

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

COMPUTATION OF POLYNOMIALS, THE LEAST DEVIATING FROM ZERO IN L_1 METRICS BY SOLVING EXTREMAL PROBLEMS

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Abstract

In this paper, we consider polynomials that deviate least from zero in the L_1 metric. Then we explicitly calculate Chebyshev polynomials of the second kind by solving extremal problems.

Keywords: Chebyshev polynomials, symmetric polynomials, extremal problems, normed spaces, L_1 space, Weierstrass theorem, Jackson theorem, polynomials deviating least from zero, Waring's inverse formula, Chebyshev polynomials of the second kind, approximation theory, optimization methods.

1. Introduction

Consider normed spaces $L_1([-1;1])$ of functions $x(t)$ measurable on the interval $[-1;1]$ such that the value is finite:

$$\|f(x(\cdot))\|_{L_1([-1;1])} := \int_{-1}^1 |x(t)| dt.$$

The general statement of the problem of polynomials deviating least from zero is as follows:

$n-1$

Among the polynomials $p_{n-1} \in P_{n-1}$, among polynomials of the form $p_{n-1}(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} x_k t^k$, $k=0$ find the one that delivers the minimum in the task

$$f_{n1}(x) = \left\| t^n + p_{n-1} \right\|_{L_1([-1;1])} = \left\| t^n + \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} x_k t^k \right\|_{L_1([-1;1])} \rightarrow \min. \quad (P)$$

Theorem 3.1 ([4]). *Function $f_{n1}(x)$ is convex, continuous, and grows at infinity.*

The function $f_{n1}(\cdot)$ is convex, continuous in x , and the solution in the problem exists according to the Weierstrass theorem and its corollary.

Theorem 3.2 (Weierstrass). *A continuous function on a non-empty bounded closed subset of a finite-dimensional space (compact set) reaches its absolute maximum and minimum.*

We single out a simple consequence of this theorem. **Corollary 1.** *If the function f is continuous on the space R^n and*

$$\lim_{|x| \rightarrow \infty} f(x) = +\infty$$

then it reaches its absolute minimum on any closed subset of R^n (not necessarily bounded). A similar statement for the absolute maximum holds if

$$\lim_{|x| \rightarrow \infty} f(x) = -\infty.$$

Let us prove that when a continuous function is approximated by algebraic polynomials of best approximation in the corresponding metrics of the spaces L_1 and C is unique. **Definition 1.** *Consider a system of real functions*

$$f_0(t), f_1(t), \dots, f_n(t),$$

continuous on the segment $[a;b]$. Consider

$$f(t) = \mu_0 f_0(t) + \mu_1 f_1(t) + \dots + \mu_n f_n(t)$$

for arbitrary coefficients $\mu_0, \dots, \mu_n$. Let each $f_i(t)$ have at most n distinct zeros on (a,b) . Such a system will be called a Chebyshev system with respect to the interval $(a;b)$.

Theorem 3.3 (Jackson). *If any non-zero polynomial in a system of linearly independent continuous ones on the segment $[a;b]$ of functions has at most n changes of sign on the interval $(a;b)$, then for any function $f \in C([a;b])$ there exists a unique polynomial of best approximation in the metric of the space $L_1([a;b])$ in this system.*

Theorem 3.4 (Haar). For any function $f \in C([a;b])$ there is a unique polynomial of best approximation in the metric of the space $C([a;b])$ with respect to the system of linearly independent continuous ones on the interval $[a; b]$ functions if and only if any non-zero polynomial in this system of functions has on $[a;b]$ at most n different zeros.

In other words, a system of functions is Chebyshev if and only if it satisfies the condition Haar.

Example 1. The system of algebraic polynomials $\{1, t, \dots, t^n\}$ satisfies the Haar condition on any interval $[a;b]$, since any non-trivial polynomial $\sum_{k=0}^n C_k t^k$ has at most n different zeros on the interval $(a;b)$, and, hence, is Chebyshevskaya.

It follows from the above example and the theorems of Jackson and Haar that when a continuous function is approximated by algebraic polynomials, the element of best approximation in the corresponding metrics of the spaces L_1 and C is unique. Let us denote the solution of the problem by x , the value by ϕ_{n1} , and the corresponding polynomial by $T_{n1}(\cdot)$.

In this way,

$$T_{n1}(t) = t^n + \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \hat{x}_k t^k, \quad \phi_{n1} = \left\| T_{n1}(\cdot) \right\|_{L_1([-1;1])}$$

The polynomial $T_{n1}(\cdot)$ is called the polynomial that deviates least from zero in the metric $L_1([-1;1])$.

2. Polynomials deviating least from zero

We introduce several auxiliary theorems that we will need to calculate polynomials.

Lemma 1. Let $f(t)$ be a piecewise continuous function on the segment $[a;b]$ and

$$\int_a^b t^k f(t) dt = 0, \quad k = 0, \dots, n-1.$$

Then the function $f(\cdot)$ changes sign on the interval $(a;b)$ at least n times.

Lemma 2. The polynomial $T_{nq}(\cdot)$ for $1 \leq q \leq \infty$ has exactly n zeros on the interval $(-1;1)$

Theorem 4.1. In the space $L_p([-a;a])$, $1 \leq p \leq \infty$, an even function is approximated by an even polynomial, and an odd function is approximated by odd polynomial.

$$\hat{p}(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \hat{x}_k t^k$$

Proof. Take a function $f(t)$. Let the polynomial $\hat{p}(t)$ is a polynomial of best approximation for it, i.e.,

$$\left\| f(t) - \hat{p}(t) \right\|_{L_p} = \inf_{p \in \mathcal{P}_{n-1}} \left\| f(t) - p(t) \right\|_{L_p}$$

Due to the symmetry with respect to zero of the segment $[-a;a]$ for an even function $f(t)$ we have

$$\left\| f(t) - \hat{p}(t) \right\|_{L_p} = \left\| f(-t) - \hat{p}(-t) \right\|_{L_p} = \left\| f(t) - \hat{p}(-t) \right\|_{L_p}$$

Hence, due to the uniqueness of the best approximation polynomial $\hat{p}(-t) = p(t)$. Hence,

the polynomial $p(t)$ is even. Similarly, due to the symmetry with respect to zero of the

segment $[-a;a]$ for the odd function $f(t)$ we have $\|f(t) - p(t)\|_{L_p} = \|f(-t) - p(-t)\|_{L_p} = \|-f(t) - p(-t)\|_{L_p} = \|f(t) - (-p(-t))\|_{L_p}$.

Hence, due to the uniqueness of the best approximation polynomial $p(t) = -p(-t) \iff$

$p(-t) = -p(t)$. Hence, the polynomial $p(t)$ odd. □

Let us formulate a necessary condition for an extremum of I order in a finitedimensional unconstrained problem, which is an analog of Fermat's theorem.

Theorem 4.2. If $\hat{x} = (\hat{x}_1, \dots, \hat{x}_n) \in \text{locestr} f$ -- point of local extremum of the function of n variables $f(x_1, \dots, x_n)$ and the function $f \in D(x)$ is differentiable at the point x , then

$$f'(\hat{x}) = 0 \iff \frac{\partial f(\hat{x})}{\partial x_1} = \dots = \frac{\partial f(\hat{x})}{\partial x_n} = 0$$

3. Symmetric polynomials

Definition 2. Polynomial $P(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ is called symmetric, if for any permutation $x_{i1}, x_{i2}, \dots, x_{in}$ variables $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n$

$$P(x_{i1}, x_{i2}, \dots, x_{in}) = P(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n).$$

Definition 3. Polynomials

$$\sigma_k(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \begin{cases} 1, & k = 0, \\ \sum_{1 \leq i_1 < \dots < i_k \leq n} x_{i_1} \dots x_{i_k}, & 1 \leq k \leq n, \\ 0, & k > n, \end{cases}$$

are called *elementary symmetric polynomials of the kth degree*.

Let's write out elementary symmetric polynomials:

$$\sigma_1(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n; \sigma_2(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = x_1x_2 + x_1x_3 + \dots + x_{n-1}x_n; \\ \sigma_3(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = x_1x_2x_3 + x_1x_2x_4 + \dots + x_{n-2}x_{n-1}x_n; \dots$$

Definition 4. For $k \in \mathbb{N}$, a polynomial of the form $S_k(x_1, \dots, x_n) = x_1^k + \dots + x_n^k$ is called the *power sum of the kth degree*.

For example,

$$S_1(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = x_1 + \dots + x_n; \\ S_2(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = x_1^2 + \dots + x_n^2; \\ S_3(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = x_1^3 + \dots + x_n^3; \\ S_4(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = x_1^4 + \dots + x_n^4;$$

....

Obviously, the polynomials $\sigma_k(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ and $S_k(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ are symmetric polynomials.

Theorem 5.1 (Waring's formula). For any $k \in \mathbb{N}$ the formula

$$S_k = k \sum_{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n} (-1)^{k+\alpha_1+\dots+\alpha_n} \frac{(\alpha_1 + \dots + \alpha_n - 1)!}{\alpha_1! \dots \alpha_n!} \sigma_1^{\alpha_1} \dots \sigma_n^{\alpha_n},$$

where the sum is taken over all sets of non-negative integers $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n$ satisfying the equality $\alpha_1 + 2\alpha_2 + \dots + n\alpha_n = k$. Here $S_k = S_k(x_1, \dots, x_n)$, $\sigma_i = \sigma_i(x_1, \dots, x_n)$, $i = 1, \dots, n$.

For example,

$$S_1 = \sigma_1; \\ S_2 = \sigma_1^2 - 2\sigma_2; \\ S_3 = \sigma_1^3 - 3\sigma_1\sigma_2 + 3\sigma_3; S_4 = \sigma_1^4 - 4\sigma_1^2\sigma_2 + 2\sigma_2^2 + 4\sigma_1\sigma_3 - 4\sigma_4.$$

Theorem 5.2 (Waring's inverse formula). For any $k \in \mathbb{N}$ the formula

$$\sigma_k = \sum_{\beta_1, \dots, \beta_n} \frac{(-1)^{k+\beta_1+\dots+\beta_n}}{\beta_1! \dots \beta_n!} S_1^{\beta_1} \left(\frac{S_2}{2}\right)^{\beta_2} \dots \left(\frac{S_n}{n}\right)^{\beta_n},$$

where the sum is taken over all sets of non-negative integers $\beta_1, \dots, \beta_n$ satisfying $\beta_1 + 2\beta_2 + \dots + n\beta_n = k$. Here $\sigma_k = \sigma_k(x_1, \dots, x_n)$, $S_i = S_i(x_1, \dots, x_n)$, $i = 1, \dots, n$.

For example, $\sigma_1 = x_1 + \dots + x_n$; $\sigma_2 = x_1x_2 + \dots + x_{n-1}x_n$; $\sigma_3 = x_1x_2x_3 + \dots + x_{n-2}x_{n-1}x_n$; $\sigma_4 = x_1x_2x_3x_4 + \dots + x_{n-3}x_{n-2}x_{n-1}x_n$.

4. Computation of Chebyshev polynomials of the second kind

Let's solve the problem of finding Chebyshev polynomials of the second kind and express it in terms of symmetric polynomials.

$$\int_{-1}^1 |t^2 + x_1t + x_0| dt \rightarrow \min.$$

Example 2.

Solution. Since an even function t^2 in the space $L([-1;1])$ is approximated by an even

polynomial, then $x_1 = 0$. Function $f(x_0) = \int_{-1}^1 |t^2 + x_0| dt$ is convex and differentiable. A necessary and sufficient condition for the minimum of such a function is:

$$\frac{df(\hat{x})}{dx_0} = 0 \iff \int_{-1}^1 \text{sign}(t^2 + \hat{x}_0) dt = 0. \quad (1)$$

By Lemma 2, the polynomial $T_{21} = t^2 + \hat{x}_0$ changes sign twice on the interval $(-1;1)$. Let's denote the sign change points $\pm \xi_1$.

Then, by virtue of relation (1), we get:

$$\int_{-1}^1 dt - \int_{-\xi_1}^{\xi_1} dt + \int_{\xi_1}^1 dt = 0 \iff$$

Figure 1:

$$\iff -\xi_1 - (-1) - \xi_1 - \xi_1 + 1 - \xi_1 = 0 \iff \xi_1 = \frac{1}{2}$$

Hence

$$T_{21} = (t + \xi_1)(t - \xi_1) = t^2 - \xi_1^2 = t^2 - S_2 = t^2 - \sigma_1^2 = t^2 - \frac{1}{4}$$

Answer. $t^2 - \frac{1}{4}$.

$$\int_{-1}^1 |t^3 + x_2 t^2 + x_1 t + x_0| dt \rightarrow \min.$$

Example 3.₋₁

Solution. Since the odd function t^3 in the space $L([-1;1])$ is approximated by an odd polynomial, then $x_2 = x_0$

= 0. Function $f(x_1) = \int_{-1}^1 |t^3 + x_1 t| dt$ is convex and differentiable.

A necessary and sufficient condition for the minimum of such a function is:

$$\frac{df(\hat{x})}{dx_1} = 0 \iff \int_{-1}^1 t \operatorname{sign}(t^3 + \hat{x}_1 t) dt = 0 \tag{2}$$

By Lemma 2, the polynomial $T_{31} = t^3 + \hat{x}_1 t$ on the interval $(-1;1)$ changes sign three times: at the points $\pm \xi_1$ and zero at the point.

Then, by virtue of relation (2), we get:

$$\iff \frac{-\xi_1^2 + 1 - \xi_1^2 - \xi_1^2 + 1 - \xi_1^2}{2} = 0 \iff \xi_1^2 = \frac{1}{2}$$

Therefore $T_{31} = t(t + \xi_1)(t - \xi_1) = t^3 - \xi_1^2 t = t^3 - S_2 t = t^3 - \sigma_1^2 t = t^3 - \frac{1}{2} t$.

Answer. $t^3 - \frac{1}{2} t$.

Figure 2:

$$\int_{-1}^1 |t^4 + x_3 t^3 + x_2 t^2 + x_1 t + x_0| dt \rightarrow \min.$$

Example 4.₋₁

Solution. Since an even function t^4 in the space $L([-1;1])$ is approximated by an even

polynomial, then $x_3 = x_1 = 0$. Function $f(x_1) = \int_{-1}^1 |t^4 + x_2 t^2 + x_0| dt$ is convex and differentiable. A necessary and sufficient condition for the minimum of such a function is:

$$f'(\hat{x}) = 0 \iff \begin{cases} \frac{\partial f(\hat{x})}{\partial x_0} = 0, \\ \frac{\partial f(\hat{x})}{\partial x_2} = 0, \end{cases} \iff \begin{cases} \int_{-1}^1 \text{sign}(t^4 + \hat{x}_2 t^2 + \hat{x}_0) dt = 0, \\ \int_{-1}^1 t^2 \text{sign}(t^4 + \hat{x}_2 t^2 + \hat{x}_0) dt = 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

By Lemma 2, the polynomial $T_{41} = t^4 + \hat{x}_2 t^2 + \hat{x}_0$ on the interval $(-1;1)$ changes sign four times: at the points $\pm \xi_1, \pm \xi_2$.

Figure 3:

Then, using the fact that the subplay expression is an even function, then from (3) we get:

$$\begin{cases} \int_0^{\xi_1} dt - \int_{\xi_1}^{\xi_2} dt + \int_{\xi_2}^1 dt = 0, \\ \int_0^{\xi_1} t^2 dt - \int_{\xi_1}^{\xi_2} t^2 dt + \int_{\xi_2}^1 t^2 dt = 0, \end{cases} \iff \begin{cases} \xi_1 - (\xi_2 - \xi_1) + (1 - \xi_2) = 0, \\ \frac{\xi_1^3 - (\xi_2^3 - \xi_1^3) + (1 - \xi_2^3)}{3} = 0, \end{cases} \iff \begin{cases} \xi_1 + (-\xi_2) = -\frac{1}{2} = S_1, \\ \xi_1^3 + (-\xi_2)^3 = -\frac{1}{2} = S_3. \end{cases}$$

$T_{41} = (t + \xi_1)(t - \xi_1)(t + \xi_2)(t - \xi_2) = (t^2 - \xi_1^2)(t^2 - \xi_2^2) = t^4 - (\xi_1^2 + \xi_2^2)t^2 + \xi_1^2 \xi_2^2$. We use the well-known Waring formulas and find $\xi_1^2 \xi_2^2$ and $\xi_1^2 + \xi_2^2$. From $S_3 = \sigma_1^3 - 3\sigma_1 \sigma_2$ we have that:

$$-\frac{1}{2} = \left(-\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 - 3\left(-\frac{1}{2}\right)\sigma_2 \iff \frac{3}{2}\sigma_2 = -\frac{3}{8} \Rightarrow \xi_1(-\xi_2) = \sigma_2 = -\frac{1}{4} \iff \xi_1^2 \xi_2^2 = \frac{1}{16}$$

By Waring's formula $S_2 = \sigma_1^2 - 2\sigma_2$ we have

$$\xi_1^2 + \xi_2^2 = \left(-\frac{1}{2}\right)^2 + 2 \cdot \frac{1}{4} = \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{2} = \frac{3}{4}$$

Thus, we get

$$T_{41} = t^4 - S_2 t^2 + \frac{(S_1^2 - S_2)^2}{4} = t^4 - (\sigma_1^2 - 2\sigma_2)t^2 + \sigma_2^2 = t^4 - \frac{3}{4}t^2 + \frac{1}{16}$$

Answer. $t^4 - \frac{3}{4}t^2 + \frac{1}{16}$.

$$\int_{-1}^1 |t^5 + x_4 t^4 + x_3 t^3 + x_2 t^2 + x_1 t + x_0| dt \rightarrow \min.$$

Example 5.⁻¹

Solution. Since the odd function t^5 in the space $L([-1;1])$ is approximated by an odd

$$f'(\hat{x}) = 0 \iff \begin{cases} \frac{\partial f(\hat{x})}{\partial x_1} = 0, \\ \frac{\partial f(\hat{x})}{\partial x_3} = 0, \end{cases} \iff \begin{cases} \int_{-1}^1 t \operatorname{sign}(t^5 + \hat{x}_3 t^3 + \hat{x}_1 t) dt = 0, \\ \int_{-1}^1 t^3 \operatorname{sign}(t^5 + \hat{x}_3 t^3 + \hat{x}_1 t) dt = 0 \end{cases}$$

$$f(x_1, x_3) = \int_{-1}^1 |t^5 + x_3 t^3 + x_1 t| dt$$

polynomial, then $x_4 = x_2 = x_0 = 0$. Function is convex and differentiable. A necessary and sufficient condition for the minimum of such a function is: (4)

By Lemma 2, the polynomial $T_{51} = t^5 + \hat{x}_3 t^3 + \hat{x}_1 t$ on the interval $(-1;1)$ changes sign five times: at the points $\pm \xi_1, \pm \xi_2$ and at zero.

Then, by virtue of relation (4), we get:

Figure 4:

$$\int_{-1}^1 -tdt + \int_{-1}^{-\xi_2} tdt - \int_{-\xi_2}^{-\xi_1} tdt + \int_{-\xi_1}^0 tdt - \int_0^{\xi_1} tdt + \int_{\xi_1}^{\xi_2} tdt - \int_{\xi_2}^1 tdt = 0 \iff$$

$$\iff \frac{-(\xi_1^2 - 1) + \xi_1^2 - \xi_2^2 + \xi_1^2 + \xi_1^2 - (\xi_2^2 - \xi_1^2) + 1 - \xi_2^2}{2} = 0 \iff \xi_1^2 - \xi_2^2 = -\frac{1}{2}.$$

$$-\int_{-1}^{-\xi_2} t^3 dt + \int_{-\xi_2}^{-\xi_1} t^3 dt - \int_{-\xi_1}^0 t^3 dt + \int_0^{\xi_1} t^3 dt - \int_{\xi_1}^{\xi_2} t^3 dt + \int_{\xi_2}^1 t^3 dt = 0 \iff$$

$$\iff \frac{-(\xi_1^4 - 1) + \xi_1^4 - \xi_2^4 + \xi_1^4 + \xi_1^4 - (\xi_2^4 - \xi_1^4) + 1 - \xi_2^4}{4} = 0 \iff \xi_1^4 - \xi_2^4 = -\frac{1}{2}.$$

$$T_{51} = t(t + \xi_1)(t - \xi_1)(t + \xi_2)(t - \xi_2) = t(t^2 - \xi_1^2)(t^2 - \xi_2^2) = t^5 - (\xi_1^2 + \xi_2^2)t^3 + \xi_1^2 \xi_2^2 t.$$

We

need to find the values $\xi_1^2 + \xi_2^2$ and $\xi_1^2 \xi_2^2$. $\xi_1^4 - \xi_2^4 = (\xi_1^2 - \xi_2^2)(\xi_1^2 + \xi_2^2) = -\frac{1}{2} \Rightarrow (\xi_1^2 + \xi_2^2) = S_2 = 1$

$$\begin{cases} \xi_1^2 - \xi_2^2 = -\frac{1}{2}, \\ \xi_1^4 + \xi_2^4 = -\frac{1}{2}. \end{cases} \iff \begin{cases} \xi_1^2 - \xi_2^2 = -\frac{1}{2}, \\ (\xi_1^2 - \xi_2^2)(\xi_1^2 + \xi_2^2) = -\frac{1}{2}. \end{cases} \iff \begin{cases} \xi_1^2 - \xi_2^2 = -\frac{1}{2}, \\ \xi_1^2 + \xi_2^2 = S_2 = 1, \end{cases} \iff \xi_1^2 \xi_2^2 = \frac{3}{16}$$

Hence

$$T_{51} = t^5 - S_2 t^3 + \frac{(S_1^2 - S_2)^2}{4} t = t^5 - (\sigma_1^2 - 2\sigma_2) t^3 + \sigma_2^2 t = t^5 - t^3 + \frac{3}{16} t.$$

Answer. $t^5 - t^3 + \frac{3}{16} t.$

$$\int_{-1}^1 |t^n + x_{n-1} t^{n-1} + \dots + x_1 t + x_0| dt \rightarrow \min.$$

Example 6.-1

Solution. Let $n = 2k$. Since by *Theorem 2.5* an even function t^{2k} in the space $L([-1;1])$ is approximated by an even polynomial, then $x_1 = x_3 = \dots = x_{n-3} = x_{n-1} = 0$.

$$\int_{-1}^1 \text{Function } f(x_0, x_2, \dots, x_{n-2}) = \int_{-1}^1 |t^n + x_{n-2}t^{n-2} + \dots + x_0| dt \text{ is convex and differentiable.}$$

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial f(\hat{x})}{\partial x_0} = 0, \\ \frac{\partial f(\hat{x})}{\partial x_2} = 0, \\ \dots \\ \frac{\partial f(\hat{x})}{\partial x_{n-2}} = 0, \end{cases} \iff \begin{cases} \int_{-1}^1 \text{sign}(t^n + \hat{x}_{n-2}t^{n-2} + \dots + \hat{x}_0) dt = 0, \\ \int_{-1}^1 t^2 \text{sign}(t^n + \hat{x}_{n-2}t^{n-2} + \dots + \hat{x}_0) dt = 0, \\ \dots \\ \int_{-1}^1 t^{n-2} \text{sign}(t^n + \hat{x}_{n-2}t^{n-2} + \dots + \hat{x}_0) dt = 0 \end{cases}$$

A necessary and sufficient condition for the minimum of such a function is:

$$T_{n1} = t^n + \hat{x}_{n-2}t^{n-2} + \dots + \hat{x}_2t^2 + \hat{x}_0, \\ \pm \xi_1, \dots, \pm \xi_{\frac{n}{2}}$$

Figure 5:

By Lemma 2, the polynomial on the interval $(-1;1)$ changes sign n times. Let us denote the sign change points.

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{-1}^{-\xi_k} dt - \int_{-\xi_k}^{\xi_{k-1}} dt + \dots - \int_{-\xi_1}^{\xi_1} dt + \int_{\xi_1}^{\xi_2} dt + \dots - \int_{\xi_{n/2-1}}^{\xi_{n/2}} dt + \int_{\xi_{n/2}}^1 dt \\ & = 0; \\ & \iff \int_{-1}^{-\xi_k} t^2 dt - \int_{-\xi_k}^{\xi_{k-1}} t^2 dt + \dots - \int_{-\xi_1}^{\xi_1} t^2 dt + \int_{\xi_1}^{\xi_2} t^2 dt + \dots - \int_{\xi_{n/2-1}}^{\xi_{n/2}} t^2 dt + \int_{\xi_{n/2}}^1 t^2 dt = 0; \\ & \iff \begin{cases} -\xi_k^3 + 1 - \xi_{k-1}^3 - \xi_k^3 + \dots - \xi_k^3 - \xi_{k-1}^3 + 1 - \xi_k^3 = 0; \\ -\xi_k^3 + 1 - \xi_{k-1}^3 - \xi_k^3 + \dots - \xi_k^3 - \xi_{k-1}^3 + 1 - \xi_k^3 = 0; \\ \dots \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} -\xi_k^{n-1} + 1 - \xi_{k-1}^{n-1} - \xi_k^{n-1} + \dots - \xi_k^{n-1} - \xi_{k-1}^{n-1} + 1 - \xi_k^{n-1} &= 0, \\ \xi_k^{n-1} + \xi_{k-1}^{n-1} + \dots + \xi_2^{n-1} + \xi_1^{n-1} &= S_{n-1} = -\frac{1}{2}. \end{aligned} \right.$$

$$\begin{aligned} T_{n1} &= (t - \xi_1)(t + \xi_1) \dots (t - \xi_k)(t + \xi_k) = t^n - \sum_{i=1}^k \xi_i^2 t^{n-2} + \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{j=1}^k \xi_i^2 \xi_j^2 t^{n-4} + \\ &\dots + (-1)^{k-1} \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{j=1}^k \dots \sum_{m=1}^k \xi_i^2 \xi_j^2 \dots \xi_m^2 t^2 + (-1)^k \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{j=1}^k \dots \sum_{m=1}^k \sum_{p=1}^k \xi_i^2 \xi_j^2 \dots \xi_m^2 \xi_p^2 = \\ &= t^n + \sum_{l=1}^{k-1} (-1)^l t^{n-2l} (\sigma_l^2 - 2\sigma_{l-1}\sigma_{l+1} + \sigma_{l+2}) + (-1)^k \sigma_k^2, \\ &\iff \left\{ \begin{aligned} \xi_k^3 + \xi_{k-1}^3 + \dots + \xi_2^3 + \xi_1^3 &= S_3 = -\frac{1}{2} \\ \xi_k + \xi_{k-1} + \dots + \xi_1 + \xi_1 &= S_1 = -\frac{1}{2}; \end{aligned} \right. \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\sigma_l^2 - 2\sigma_{l-1}\sigma_{l+1} + \sigma_{l+2} = \sum_{n=1}^k \dots \sum_{n=1}^k \underbrace{\xi_n^2 \dots \xi_m^2}_l$$

$l = 1, 2, \dots, k-1$ and

$$\sigma_k = \sum_{\beta_1, \dots, \beta_n} \frac{(-1)^{k+\beta_1+\dots+\beta_n}}{\beta_1! \dots \beta_n!} S_1^{\beta_1} \left(\frac{S_2}{2}\right)^{\beta_2} \dots \left(\frac{S_n}{n}\right)^{\beta_n}$$

And the sum is taken over all sets of non-negative integers $\beta_1, \dots, \beta_n$ satisfying the equality $\beta_1 + 2\beta_2 + \dots + n\beta_n = k$.

Let $n = 2k + 1$. Since by *Theorem 2.5* the odd function t^{2k+1} in the space $L([-1;1])$ is approximated by an odd polynomial, then $x_0 = x_2 = \dots = x_{n-3} = x_{n-1} = 0$. Function

$$f(x_1, x_3, \dots, x_{n-2}) = \int_{-1}^1 |t^n + x_{n-2}t^{n-2} + \dots + x_3t^3 + x_1t| dt \text{ is convex and differentiable. A}$$

necessary and sufficient condition for the minimum of such a function is:

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} \frac{\partial f(\hat{x})}{\partial x_1} &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial f(\hat{x})}{\partial x_3} &= 0, \\ \dots & \\ \frac{\partial f(\hat{x})}{\partial x_{n-2}} &= 0, \end{aligned} \right. \iff \left\{ \begin{aligned} \int_{-1}^1 t \operatorname{sign}(t^n + \hat{x}_{n-2}t^{n-2} + \dots + \hat{x}_0) dt &= 0, \\ \int_{-1}^1 t^3 \operatorname{sign}(t^n + \hat{x}_{n-2}t^{n-2} + \dots + \hat{x}_0) dt &= 0, \\ \dots & \\ \int_{-1}^1 t^{n-2} \operatorname{sign}(t^n + \hat{x}_{n-2}t^{n-2} + \dots + \hat{x}_0) dt &= 0 \end{aligned} \right.$$

By Lemma 2, the polynomial $T_{n1} = t^n + \hat{x}_{n-2}t^{n-2} + \dots + \hat{x}_3t^3 + \hat{x}_1t$ on the interval $(-1;1)$ changes sign n times. Denote the sign change points $\pm \zeta_1, \dots, \pm \zeta_{(n-1)/2}$ and $\zeta = 0$.

Then, by virtue of the resulting system, we have:

$$T_{21} = t^2 - \sigma_1^2 = t^2 - S_2 = t^2 - \frac{1}{4};$$

$$T_{31} = t^3 - \sigma_1^2 t = t^3 - S_2 t = t^3 - \frac{1}{2}t;$$

$$T_{41} = t^4 - (\sigma_1^2 - 2\sigma_2)t^2 + \sigma_2^2 = t^4 - S_2 t^2 + \left(\frac{S_1^2}{2} - \frac{S_2}{2}\right)^2 = t^4 - \frac{3}{4}t^2 + \frac{1}{16};$$

$$T_{51} = t^5 - (\sigma_1^2 - 2\sigma_2)t^3 + \sigma_2^2 t = t^5 - S_2 t^3 + \left(\frac{S_1^2}{2} - \frac{S_2}{2}\right)^2 t = t^5 - t^3 + \frac{3}{16}t;$$

$$T_{61} = t^6 - (\sigma_1^2 - 2\sigma_2)t^4 + (\sigma_2^2 - 2\sigma_1\sigma_3)t^2 - \sigma_3^2 = t^6 - S_2 t^4 + \frac{1}{2}(S_2^2 - S_4)t^2 - \sigma_3^2 = \\ = t^6 - \frac{5}{4}t^4 + \frac{3}{8}t^2 - \frac{1}{64};$$

$$T_{71} = t^7 - (\sigma_1^2 - 2\sigma_2)t^5 + (\sigma_2^2 - 2\sigma_1\sigma_3)t^3 - \sigma_3^2 t = t^7 - S_2 t^5 + \frac{1}{2}(S_2^2 - S_4)t^3 - \sigma_3^2 t = \\ = t^7 - \frac{3}{2}t^5 + \frac{5}{8}t^3 - \frac{1}{16}t.$$

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MAXIMISATION OF CONDITIONAL MUTUAL INFORMATION

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Abstract

In this paper we consider mutual information for a pair of random variables and find a third variable (condition) that maximise conditional mutual information of three of them.

Keywords: Mutual information, conditional mutual information, entropy, information inequality, Lagrange theorem, conditional extremum.

1 Solution

Let A , B and X take two values for convenience. We will solve the problem using methods from the optimal control course. In entropy, we take the natural logarithm for ease of differentiation. Consider $I(A;B|X)$ as a function of p_{ijk} :

$$I(A; B|X) = H(A, X) + H(B, X) - H(A, B, X) - H(X) = \\ = \sum_{i,k} p_{ik} \log(p_{ik}) = \sum_{i,k} \left(\sum_j p_{ijk} \right) \log \left(\sum_j p_{ijk} \right) \log(p_k) =$$

Here the values A have the index i , the values B have the index j , the values X have the index k . Now let's express everything in terms of p_{ijk} :